

Least squares approximation of ECG signals with rational functions

Software_02: oneper.f95

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1. Abstract

This description is closely related to an **older article** of the same main title [1], reading this article will make it easier to understand more. It mostly discusses the working principle of our ECG Feature Extraction (FEX) "**progr1-123**" program. This program system does not extract the features (FEX) automatically, but with frequent operator interaction. Between the steps, he draws the diagram necessary for further decisions, and based on this, the operator determines the next step of the program.

In a previous description, we dealt with the operation and use of the **first** preparatory "**prep**" program [8]. In the following description, we deal with the operation and use of the **second** preparatory program, the "**oneper**" program.

In the {[1] 4.12. *Preparation*} section of the mentioned article, we have already briefly described the "**prep**" program. We did not write about the "**oneper**" program in the aforementioned article [1], but we briefly mentioned it in the article with the same main title but subtitled "Removing The Mains Frequency (50 Hz or 60 Hz). A New Method" [9]. The "**oneper**" program uses the results of the **prep** program.

- For a **new ECG** signal, the operator is asked for the **new identifier** (patient&serial number) (see below).
- We read the necessary data from the data calculated by the "**prep**" program.
- The selected period of the original ECG signal is read.
- We recalculate the location of the QRS with the help of the already final baselines.
{max. length of a vector= $\text{SQRT}(vx^2+vy^2+vz^2)$ }
- Filterings:
For 99Hz filtering with a high-pass filter.
The 50Hz (the mains frequency) is reduced with the "**pr50Hz**" utility [9].
- We write out the recalculated QRS location.
- Finally, we create the "**sam-oneper.txt**" file {[9], "Attachments_files-En.rtf"} containing the results.
(This is the so-called "vezérlőszalag" = "control tape" out of respect for tradition.)

This "**2. We repeat...**" section below was copied here verbatim from the description of the "**prep**" program [8]!

Note: In the *.txt format files, auxiliary comments are often included at the end of the lines used by the programs, as well as after the lines. (These comments are not used by programs.)

2. We repeat and supplement some information from the mentioned above article [1]:

The **Fortran** we use {[1] 4.4 *The norm and tools used for approximation*} and its environment:

64 bits processor, Windows 7 Professional with Service Pack 1

GNU Fortran (GCC) 4.8.1 with 0.6.2-mingw32-beta-20131004-1

This compiler is not Fortran IV or Fortran 66: "The GNU Fortran compiler supports the Fortran 77, 90 and 95 standards completely, parts of the Fortran 2003 and Fortran 2008 standards, and several vendor extensions" [3]. In addition to these modern improvements, we can use older subroutines, such as those in MINPACK, without changing the source code!

Our records uploaded in the topic of the main title can be accessed by the following search:

<https://zenodo.org/search?q=creators.name%3A%20%22Kobzos%2C%20Laszlo%22&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=bestmatch>

Since this program system **does not automatically calculate the features** (FEX), but with frequent operator interaction, we create **diagrams** for them, using **MS_EXCEL** or **GNU Octave** [4]. The **transfer of information** between the parts of our program system usually takes place in text files. So are the above programs. In these text files, we used a **decimal point** (for GNU Octave) or a **decimal comma** (for MS_EXCEL). Any text editor can be used to transform them, replacing all commas with points or vice versa.

The source code of our programs is usually provided with many **comments** for their use and possible modifications. The comments are in Hungarian. The same goes for text outputs. We hope that the English language **program descriptions** and **user guides** will be of sufficient help to understand our programs.

We use two types of character encoding:

- For Windows text files and comments: Windows-1250

- For Windows Command Prompt (~DOS) files: OEM 852

If we use Notepad++ : Encoding | Character sets | Central European | ...

The source of the ECG data used {[1] 4.5 *Data*} :

Our ECG data comes from the **PhysioNet database** [2]. From this database, 549 **anonymised** ECG data of 290 individuals can be accessed by selecting PTB. In addition to the signals, the "PTB Diagnostic ECG Database" contains other data, as well (such as: age, sex and diagnosis of the individuals, ...). Signals are sampled at 1 kHz (i.e. 1 sample per 1 millisecond), and a 1mV signal corresponds to a quantisation level of 2000. Although our method is independent of the lead system, we have mainly investigated 3 leads of the **Frank system** (vx, vy and vz; sometimes only x, y and z). Using Dower or inverse-Dower matrix transformations, the data of the conventional 12-lead system can be calculated from the Frank lead system data, and vice versa [5, 6].

The original ECG signals: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.13026/C28C71> License: Open Data Commons Attribution License v1.0

We do not deal with cases of **arrhythmia**, because these signs belong to the "should consult a cardiologist" category.

A commonly used method to extract the feature data (FEX, Feature Extraction): "A common method is to approximate the signal using a function with parameters that can be set, so that the difference between the signal and the **shapes** of the function (in the biologically relevant parts) is small. Then the parameters

of the function that approximate the signal will be considered to be characteristic of it. For this purpose, we have chosen rational functions." For approximation, the rational function was written in the root factor form {[1] 4.1. *The approximation function*}. The roots of the denominator and the numerator are called poles and zeros, respectively.

Identifying the periods used { [1] 5. Results, first paragraph } :

The signals tested are denoted as follows: s.... = serial number, p... = patient number. For example "s0025_p005". If we want to be more precise about the location within the record, we also indicate the lead and the location of the QRS. For example "s0025_p005, vz, 7009".

The coordinate system used { [1] 4.6. *The coordinate system used* } :

The **x-axis** (t-axis) of a period of a lead was determined with a method usually **used in cardiology**. That is, in the signal-free part before the P wave of the period, we identify a location where the noise is limited, or filter out the noise by "looking", and we mark the starting point of the baseline. The other point of the baseline is similarly determined at the next P wave. The line passing through these two points is called the **baseline**.

The time value of the maximum point of the signal energy (proportional to the square of the voltage) was chosen as the **origin**. This point is always within the QRS-complex. In more detail: In the case of a **Frank lead** system, since it is orthogonal in space, we used the Pythagorean Theorem to determine the curve of the voltage vector length from the vx, vy, vz leads. Its maximum indicates the maximum activity of the electrical signal of the heart. Because of the noise on the leads, we instead cut the curve at 95% of the maximum voltage vector and choose the middle point between the two intersections as the time value of the origin. Since this does not usually coincide with the location of the sampling point, we round to the nearest location.

If we do not use a Frank lead system, but a 12-lead system, then the location of the origin can be determined in the same way using the (nearly perpendicular) V6, II and $-0.5 \times V2$ leads [7].

Addendum to this: In programs, the last character of the variable name is often **A** or **R**. This usually means **Absolute** or **Relative**. For example: i_P1_loc**A**. For the ECG signal downloaded from the database, the character **A** indicates the distance calculated from the starting point of the signal, while **R** indicates the distance calculated from the starting point of the selected period (P, QRS and T). In those programs that deal with only one period, **A** indicates the distance from the beginning of the period, while **R** indicates the (signed) distance from the QRS wave.

We wrote at the beginning of all our programs written in Fortran (.f95) that we do not use automatic type declaration (**implicit none**). But **usually** the first letter of **INTEGER** variables is "I, J, K, L, M, or N". The **LOGICAL** variables **usually** start with "log_" and **CHARACTER** variables with "ch".

The number of parameters of the above-mentioned function is often listed in programs, data files and diagrams. For example, variable names: ch_fajt12, i_P_fajt1, i_P_fajt2, i_fajt2. For example in figures: P35 "stands for wave P, 3 is the number of parameters of the numerator (including the leading coefficient **d**), while 5 is the number of pole **pairs** (factors) of the denominator. Thus, the number of parameters of the approximation is $3 + 2 \times 5 = 13$."

The two six-character numbers in the data files and in the figures are the timestamp. This 2×6 digit number (yymmdd hhmmss) means "year month day hour minute second".

In our figures containing a single period:

- On the millimeter-scale paper commonly used in ECG machines, the 1×1 mm square of ECG signals (so-called “small square”) this corresponds to 40 points (40 ms)×200 points (0.1 mV) in our drawings. This 40 points×200 points grid - enlarged according to the size of the figure - shown on all our diagrams containing ECG signals.

- Drawing the imaginary values of the roots on the same diagram as the ECG signals we multiplied them by 50, 70, 7 and 50 for the P, QRS, T and Ta waves, respectively (for old ECG signals: 50, 100, 10, -).

- In the figures, the poles are marked with **x** and the zeros with **o**.

- In the figures, only one of the two conjugated complex roots was shown, namely always the one falling towards the momentary value of the signal.

3. Program Description

The purpose of the **"oneper"** program is to collect the data of the selected ECG period for the "progr1-123" program.

Input UNITS:

keyboard: patient&serial number

101 qrs_index.txt, {[8] **3. Program Description**, Output: 128}

111 ciklus.txt, for the outer loop, reading the sequence number and the final value, (and then writes the new values to the same place)

131 one111per.txt, {[8] **3. Program Description**, Output: 126}

141 43-97-995-1321-22-filter.txt, 99Hz filter

Octave remez 0.0 97.0 99.5 500.0 Hz, 1320+1 (grid=22) high-pass filter

221 stream.xyz, the original ECG signal

233 stream.xyz, the original ECG signal, (to identify the ECG signal and patient&serial number)

235 AUXX\streamS, is the ECG signal old or new? (to identify the ECG signal and patient&serial number)

271 AUXX\sorsz_pac.txt, old identifier (to identify the ECG signal and patient&serial number)

Output UNITS:

screen: location of the QRS (old-new, relative-absolute)

104 sam-oneper.txt, {[9], "Attachments_files-En.rtf"}, "control tape"

112 ciklus.txt, for the outer loop, (reading the sequence number and the final value,) and then writes the new values to the same place

120 AUXX\param-?.txt (x y z), location of the QRS (old-new, relative-absolute)

236 AUXX\streamS, the first 16 bytes of the stream.xyz file, (for comparison)

272 AUXX\sorsz_pac.txt, new patient&serial number

INCLUDE **"koz_par_2.f95"** ! so that a couple of parameters in the prep.f95 and oneper.f95 programs are the same.

If these values ("**i_balsz**", "**i_jobbsz**") are changed in the "**prep.f95**" or "**oneper.f95**" programs, both must be recompiled.

STATEMENT FUNCTION

f_alapv_st_fv(i_form_par) To calculate the points of a line passing through two points.

01~ ~~~ chapter

The patient&serial number data should belong to "**stream.xyz**":

Reading 16 bytes from the beginning of "**stream.xyz**".

Reading the 16 bytes of the previous "**stream.xyz**" from "**AUXX\streamS**".

Comparison. If not identical:

Reading the new patient&serial from the console and put it in the file "**AUXX\sorsz_pac.txt**". (for example: s0038_p007)

We put the first 16 bytes in "**AUXX\streamS**".

02~ ~~~ chapter

There is also an external program cycle (batch file), but we non-use it because there are too much of conditions for its use. For example, it is not possible to reduce the amplitude of the 50 Hz mains frequency. The data of this external program cycle (current value, final value) is contained in the "**cycle.txt**" file.

We reading from the "**cycle.txt**" file:

ciklus.txt ==> icik_, icikl_veg

If the command line that starts the program contains a 3-character long parameter (e.g.: oneper.exe abc), the program jumps from here: goto 222, (this program: 13~ ~~~ chapter), where the program will initiate the exit from this external cycle).

03~ ~~~ chapter

Reading from '**one111per.txt**':

==> i_333 the number of samples of the ECG signal period

==> jel_QRS_nb_R what point of the period was the approximate location of the QRS

Allocations

04~ ~~~ chapter

Reading the data of the selected period from the line numbered icik_ of "**qrs_index.txt**" {[8] 13~ ~~~ chapter}

==> i_QRS_hely_A, na_alap_K_A, na_alap_V_A, 3*alapv_y(1,:), alapv_y(2,:)

05~ ~~~ chapter

Reading in the data of the **99Hz filter**.

141 43-97-995-1321-22-filter.txt ==> spl_t_filt2 (:)

Octave remez 0.0 97.0 99.5 500.0 Hz, 1320+1 (grid=22) high-pass filter

The 50Hz (the mains frequency) is reduced with the "**pr50Hz**" utility [9]. (See below.)

06~ ~~~ chapter

Do we check whether the read and calculated lengths of the signal period are the same? ("**koz_par_2.f95**")

Reading the signal period from the "**stream.xyz**" file. The structure of the signal: 2 bytes vx, then 2 bytes vy, finally 2 bytes vz.

stream.xyz ==> na_vez(:, :)

07~ ~~~ chapter

We calculate the **power function** of the ECG signal (it is the square of the "vector length function"):

At a point, the value of **vx** is:

$vx(:) = na_vez(:, 1) - f_alapv_st_fv(:)$

A **pov** értéke pedig:

$vx(:)^2 + vy(:)^2 + vz(:)^2 ==> pov(:)$

08~ ~~~ chapter

We calculate the "vector length function", which is the square root of the "power function":

$SQRT(pov(:)) ==> vcl(:)$

Here, at the same time, we find the location and value of the longest vector of the period:

$max(vcl(:)) ==> vch_max, max_loc ==> i_hely_bs$

Near the maximum point of the signal, we determine the location of the QRS by level cutting. The level:

$0.95_dp \times vch_max ==> hely_basis_z$

In the vector length function, the actual location of the level intersection is determined by interpolation from the values taken at the point before and after the level intersection before the maximum location:

hely_basis_xm

Similarly after the maximum place:

hely_basis_xn

The actual QRS location is considered to be the midpoint of these two points (this is the origin of the relative locations):

$0.5_dp \times (\text{hely_basis_xm} + \text{hely_basis_xn}) \implies \text{hely_bазis}$

Or as a whole number:

$\text{NINT}(\text{hely_bазis})$

09~ ~ ~ chapter

For filtering, we need a signal wider than the ECG period, so it starts earlier (and ends later):

$\text{position1} - 6 \times \text{i_szff2} \implies \text{position1}$

Reading:

$\text{stream.xyz} \implies \text{szurt_xyz2}(:, :)$

Then we perform the filtering:

$\text{szurt_xyz2}(:, :) \implies \text{szur_s} \implies \text{szurt_xyz2}(:, :)$

10~ ~ ~ chapter

We fill the "alapv_xyz" array with the values of the baseline, but in order to show the beginning and end of the baseline section on the drawings, the upload is omitted beyond these points.

$\text{f_alapv_st_fv}(:, :) \implies \text{alapv_xyz}(:, :)$

11~ ~ ~ chapter

We write some information on the screen and in the three "AUX\param-x.txt" files.

The two values of the external cycle, and the QRS location data (old R, new R, correction, old A, new A).

12~ ~ ~ chapter

Finally, we create the "sam-oneper.txt" file {[9], "Attachments_files-En.rtf"} containing the results.

(This is the so-called "vezérlőszalag" = "control tape" out of respect for tradition.)

End of run.

13~ ~~~ chapter

Although we don't use the outer loop, this part remains inside the program. (For example, increasing the loop variable)

14~ ~~~ chapter

subroutine szur_s (ekg_s, na_ekg_filt_s, filt_s, i_tap_s)

The input parameters are respectively: the three leads of the ECG signal, the extended signal range of the filter, the FIR filter coefficients, the number of filter coefficients.

The output parameter is also ekg_s.

End of program.

3a. The pr50Hz.f95 add-on program Description

The task of the "pr50Hz" add-on program: Removing The Mains Frequency (50 Hz or 60 Hz). We wrote about this in detail in [9] in article. The purpose of the method is to eliminate or significantly reduce mains noise.

The steps of the program in brief:

- Reading the approximation parameters from the "**pr50Hz.txt**" file (see below).
- Reading the signal to be approximated.
- 99Hz noise filtering of the selected lead.
- We set the initial parameters of the approximation.
- We call the approximation subroutine. (call lmdif1).

External subroutine: fcn_6.f95. Its task is mainly to calculate function values {[9] 5.1. Method}

- Writing out the curves of the results in the "**RAJZOK\rajz50Hz.txt**" file (see below).
- If we accept this reduction of network noise, then:

The program must be restarted with any three-character command line parameter (e.g.: pr50Hz.exe cba). Then the ~50Hz sine signal that reduces network noise is transferred to the "**sam-oneper.txt**" file.

4. User Guide

The preparation of this program can be described very briefly, because most of the preparation has already been done by the "**prep**" program. The only task is to

choose which of the 5 periods mentioned in the description {[8] **3. User Guide**, 11~ ~~~ chapter, save it all (.xls)} of the "prep" program is the most average. The saved EXCEL files of the leads help with this. You will need this serial number to fill in "**ciklus.txt**". For example, if the selected cycle is the second, writing " 2 2", (2I4 format), i.e. three spaces and then the number 2, and the same again (the latter was the end value of the external cycle used earlier). Note: the single serial number of the period naturally refers to all three (vx, vy, vz) leads.

4a. The pr50Hz.f95 add-on program User Guide

The method described in [9] was used in this program. The parameters required to run the program are contained in the "pr50Hz.txt" file. The file consists of 7 lines, 7 values must be entered one per line, in I4 format:

- Serial number of the lead (if vx, then 1, if vy, then 2, and if vz, then 3).
- The location of the starting point of the **first** of the two short sections mentioned in the {[9] 5.1. Method } section.
- How many times are the section 20 points long (e.g. 2 for 40 points, because $40=2 \times 20$).
- The degree of the polynomial part of the section (if constant, then 0, if linear, then 1, finally, if square, then 2).
- Then another 3 lines, from the **second** short section.

As we wrote in the note before "**2. We repeat and ...**", there are comments at the end of the lines and at the end of the file.

While the program is running, it prints some data on the screen, the last line is the "standard deviation", i.e. the approximation error plus other noise.

The results are contained in the "**RAJZOK\rajz50Hz.txt**" file, it is worth plotting with "for example MS_EXCEL". The columns are. 1c, 2c,... = first column, second column, (and so on):

- 1c we approximate this: the selected lead - baseline - 99 Hz filter
- 2c the full approximation on the two sections
- 3c the sine part of the approximation on the two sections, continuing on the other sections as well
- 4c the polynomial part of the approximation on the two sections
- 5c 1c - 3c (approximate sine)
- 6c 1c - baseline
- 7c 6c - 3c (sine part...) + 400 (increased)

If the network noise reduction is considered adequate: The program must be restarted with any three-character command line parameter (e.g.: pr50Hz.exe cba).

5. References

- [1] Kobzos, L. (2023). FEX3-ECG/MS01,v1.0.4: Least Squares Approximation of ECG Signals with Rational Functions (1.0.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7671387>
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